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D2.1 Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape

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EU-RES	Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	✓
EU-CON	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The shifting technological, regulatory, and geopolitical dynamics demand a proactive strategy to maintain the EU's competitiveness and digital sovereignty. This report provides a comprehensive analysis of Europe's challenges and opportunities in the evolving ICT standardisation landscape.

The report explores the current state of ICT standardisation landscape, Europe's place in it, identifies key challenges, and offers preliminary policy recommendations. By conducting qualitative interviews with 30 experts and gathering secondary data, the study provides analysis of the regulatory, technological, and geopolitical drivers reshaping the ICT standardisation landscape. The research is part of the multi-phase StandICT.eu 2026 project, led by OpenForum Europe (OFE), and will further inform subsequent phases involving stakeholder consultations and case studies.

Key Findings

Market Concentration and Standardisation:

Market concentration among a few dominant technology companies creates strategic barriers to open and inclusive standardisation. Major players often avoid leading standards initiatives in areas they dominate, leading to fragmented markets and reduced interoperability.

EU Regulation and Software:

Recent EU legislation, such as the Digital Markets Act and Cyber Resilience Act, increasingly relies on harmonised standards for implementation. This regulatory framework is expanding into the software realm, placing unprecedented demands on European Standards Organisations (ESOs) to deliver compliant, high-quality standards at an accelerated pace.

Geopolitical Rivalries and Strategic Positioning:

Europe faces mounting pressure to assert its influence amidst US and Chinese strategic competition. The EU Standardisation Strategy aims to balance the need for value-based global standards with the technical neutrality required to maintain inclusive processes. This ambition is challenging, given the necessity for international collaboration. These new demands from governments increase the strains on the ESOs.

Recommendations

ESOs must ensure that broad stakeholder representation in standard development processes is not sacrificed in the pursuit of speed of standards development. Priority should stay with including small and medium-sized enterprises, civil-society, and consumer organisations. However, as software is becoming more central to ICT standards, the system needs a different approach to representation and expertise, including from non-corporate software experts.

Collaborative and flexible approaches, such as open source methodologies, should be integrated into European standardisation to streamline processes while maintaining consensus-based decision-making.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ANEC	European Association for the Coordination of Consumer Representation in Standardisation
ASF	Apache Software Foundation
CDT	Center for Democracy and Technology
CEN-CENELEC	European Committee for Standardization (CEN) and European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC)
CERRE	Centre on Regulation in Europe
CRA	EU Cyber Resilience Act
DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung (German Institute for Standardisation)
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DSA	Digital Services Act
EEA	European Economic Area
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EUOS	EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation
FSA	Fair Standards Alliance
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IPRED	Intellectual Property Rights Enforcement Directive
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
OASIS	Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards
RWTHA	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule (Aachen University)
SDO	Standards Development Organization
NSB	National Standards Body

1. INTRODUCTION

b. 1.1 Objective and Scope

This landscape report is part of the StandICT.eu 2026 project, which builds on the successes of the previous two StandICT.eu initiatives (2018-2019 and 2020-2023). StandICT.eu 2026 has been recognised as the “go-to” project for ICT standards in Europe. The project’s primary goal is to strengthen its global reach in the European ICT standardisation ecosystem through several initiatives. The Fellowship Programme provides €2,925,000 in funding over 36 months to support experts contributing to international standards. The EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation (EUOS) and Technical Working Groups (TWGs) empower ICT standardisation experts to collaborate and influence standards globally. The Standards Education Group (EUOS-SEG) focuses on training the next generation of ICT standardisation experts, working with national standardisation bodies and public-private partnerships. The Expert Advisory Group (EAG) provides strategic oversight by tapping into the working groups and technical committees of standards development organisations to tackle European priorities. Finally, the Forum on EU Strategy for ICT Standards (FOREST) aligns policy discussions with the Multi-Stakeholder Platform and the High-Level Forum on European Standardisation.

Within the StandICT.eu project’s Observatory and Technical Working Groups. Specifically, this landscape report relates to Task 2.2 and aims to explore and analyse the current state of ICT standardisation in Europe and identify challenges and opportunities. This task is led by OpenForum Europe (OFE) with partners including the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft. The objective is to understand how European competitiveness and digital sovereignty will be affected by evolving ICT standardisation trends such as the shift towards open, collaborative, and royalty-free models.

The landscape report is the first deliverable of this task (D2.1) and is part of a multiphase study that will include further analysis through six detailed case studies, additional interviews, and updates to the policy recommendations. Subsequent phases will also include comprehensive stakeholder consultation processes leading to the production of a final study.

c. 1.2 Context

The European Union (EU) faces several key geopolitical challenges in the coming decade, such as the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the trade policies of the Trump and Biden White Houses, and the rise of China — all with a myriad of direct and indirect implications. In parallel, the EU is driving the regulation of the digital markets globally, in part using its regulations to create either *de jure* (in the law) or *de facto* (in practice) standards for implementing key technologies like AI, increasing the EU’s cyber resilience or improving the interoperability and switching between vendors in concentrated digital markets.¹ Such digital regulations require adaptive ICT standards to keep the digital single market competitive and secure.

In practical terms, the approach taken by the European Commission – as expressed in its December 2022 [European Union Standardisation Strategy](#) – is to use standards to promote EU values, policy objectives, and regulatory implementation. Over the last 30 years, the European standardisation system has established over 3,600 harmonised standards,

¹ Bruegel. Dataset: EU Legislation in the Digital World [Dataset]. <https://www.bruegel.org/dataset/dataset-eu-legislation-digital-world>.

supporting compliance with EU laws and promoting interoperability and safety. To meet the evolving competitive landscape and protect Europe's competitiveness, technological sovereignty, and values, the Strategy calls for enhancing European standardisation skills, agility, and foresight to anticipate standardisation needs. The system must also adapt to the rapid pace of innovation by delivering standards swiftly while maintaining high-quality outcomes.

Moreover, as of early 2024, the EU is conducting a public consultation on Regulation 2012/1025 with the aim to keep the framework that regulates the European standardisation system remaining effective amid evolving opportunities and challenges². This evaluation will determine if the existing regulation can adequately address globalisation, public safety, and the 'twin' green and digital transitions. This was promised in the European Standardisation Strategy, and has been eagerly awaited by established and new standardisation stakeholders.

It is in this context of such a trend of accelerating demand for ICT standardisation that we can see how foundational standards for Europe's digital future. Standards can help ensure the European market remains open, competitive, and secure, while also demonstrating Europe's leading role in regulating and driving the adoption of digital technologies, which will have implications both within and beyond its borders.

This landscape report has been created within that context and aims to investigate how the European Union can effectively navigate the rapidly changing ICT standardisation landscape. Particular focus is given in the report to the ongoing paradigm shift towards collaborative, open, and royalty-free standardisation models, and the drivers behind this paradigm shift. In doing so, the report aims to identify significant trends and potential future developments in the ICT standardisation landscape that will help inform policy recommendations and future research.

The observations highlighted in this study primarily draw on qualitative research methods, which carry certain limitations regarding the generalisability of findings. The qualitative data was gathered from both on- and off-the-record interviews with a diverse cohort of stakeholders and experts with the aim of covering as much as possible of the spectrum of views on the ICT standardisation landscape. The selection criteria for interviewees included geographic diversity, sector-specific expertise, and gender balance.

Inevitably, this approach introduces a degree of subjectivity, as responses are shaped by both the interviewer's interpretations and the interviewees' perspectives. Despite these limitations, this landscape report embraces the interpretive validity of findings stemming from intuitive insights, subjective perceptions, and conjectural analysis, as a basis for this phase of the larger study. Where possible, it draws liberally from the wealth of available literature and studies to help reinforce certain findings and observations.

d. 1.3 Structure of the Report

This report is divided into four main chapters, followed by a section for discussion and conclusions, and a section for preliminary policy recommendations to address the challenges

² European Commission. Evaluation of the European Standardisation System. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13446-European-standardisation-evaluation_en.

identified in the report and to guide the development of a strategic framework for ICT standardisation in Europe.

The four main chapters that form the bulk of the report are:

- **Chapter 1:** This chapter sets the stage for the broader discussion by laying out the context and landscape for the other chapters finding, as well as by contextualising the interviews which were conducted. It describes the foundational assumptions of the analysis, such as how the primary driver of change in the ICT standardisation landscape is the *softwarisation* of society, a trend we discuss further and which is reshaping social interactions and infrastructures, affecting standardisation across the board. This chapter also introduces two secondary drivers of change explored further in subsequent chapters: *new EU regulation* and *geopolitical competition*.
- **Chapter 2:** This chapter examines digital market regulation and standardisation, with a focus on the goals and impacts. It discusses two main trends, as identified by the experts spoken to for this report. The first is *market concentration*, or the perception that major technology firms act to influence standardisation to protect their market position. The second is the *extension of EU regulation into software* – with recent changes being driven by concerns around safety and security – and how this expands the stakeholder group within the landscape, creating new demands and strains on the European standardisation system.
- **Chapter 3:** The third chapter addresses intensified geopolitical competition – particularly between Europe, the United States of America, and China – and how this is expressed within digital policy, but particularly the ICT standardisation landscape more narrowly. This report argues that these rivalries shape strategic political decisions with ramifications for standardisation processes and they impact Europe's ability to assert its standards globally. The chapter closes with a discussion of how Europe has responded to the politicisation of standardisation with demands for reform of European Standards Organisations' governance to increase the influence of national standardisation bodies.
- **Chapter 4:** This chapter brings together the many old and new demands for inclusivity in the standardisation system, and looks in-depth at the convergence of software and standards. It highlights open source as a challenge to getting effective software regulation and relevant harmonised standards, as well as how the convergence of open source and standardisation creates demands for a more inclusive and collaborative environment that incorporates diverse stakeholder interests (especially open source stakeholders who don't fit the traditional multi-stakeholder model). This chapter concludes with observations on IPR policies and norms and the friction they create when reforms are demanded by new stakeholders in the ICT standardisation landscape.

Chapter 1 can be read as a background section and relies more on secondary sources, while Chapters 2-4 are mainly structured around direct quotes from the interviews, and cover a large number of observations and points, interspersed with points of analysis.

2. RESEARCH DESIGN AND INTENT

2.1 Research Plan

This report is Phase 2 of a multi-phase study whose final report will aim to offer a comprehensive analysis of the ICT standardisation landscape across three thematic chapters. The final report will also be supported by six case studies, and it provides a set of further developed ICT-related policy recommendations that will be circulated to other interested stakeholders, such as the High-Level Forum on European Standardisation, as well as provides the foundation for helping policymakers and researchers build hypotheses to help guide further inquiry.

Phase 1: The study began with 10 off-the-record interviews to identify key trends for the 2023 paper [The Evolving ICT Standardisation Landscape](#), by the same author. Those preliminary findings developed the approach to data collection and analysis presented in this landscape report.

Phase 2: Phase 2, which this report is a part of, builds on the work done in Phase 1 and incorporates the results of a further 20 on-the-record interviews focused on discussing and elaborating the identified trends.

Phase 3A: The conclusions and initial recommendations derived from these interviews will be taken through a stakeholder consultation process, which forms the bulk of Phase 3A. The details of this process will be reported in D2.2 "Stakeholder consultation process midterm report" due in M18.

Phase 3B: In parallel with the stakeholder consultation process, six case studies that delve into the key thematic areas outlined in this landscape report will be developed and published. These case studies will aim to illustrate and explore the practical implications and applications of the trends and recommendations detailed in the broader study.

Phase 4: Upon the completion of the stakeholder consultations and case studies, the final phase of this project will result in a final report. This report will integrate all findings, refined recommendations, and the case studies, to provide a thorough and nuanced analysis to guide future research and policy development.

Given the qualitative nature of this landscape report, the findings should be interpreted with consideration to the context and sources from which they were derived, and not generalised across the entire standardisation system. We hope to comment further on the generalisability of the findings after the comprehensive stakeholder consultation process in phase 3a.

2.2 Approach and Methodology

This report is based on a holistic methodology that engages stakeholders and experts from diverse sectors. It does not look at the ICT standardisation system itself, but rather the landscape within which it exists and with which it interacts. This approach allows us to examine a broad spectrum of interests, trends, laws, and policies. The report's author acknowledges a trade-off and that breadth has been sacrificed to increase the level of detail. This decision was taken based on the complex nature of standardisation and a desire to comprehensively

address certain aspects so as to produce novel insights that may inform the European Commission's strategies.

A first phase involved conducting 10 off-the-record, background interviews of experts in the field. Foundational to these interviews was the assurance of confidentiality to the participants. Participants were informed that their contributions would be treated with the highest level of discretion. Specifically, no direct attributions are made to any individual from these 10 interviews in this landscape report or any other materials of this study. This measure was instituted to encourage open and candid discussions, ensuring that the insights gleaned were both genuine and uninhibited.

Insights from those 10 interviews were used to define the key trends and data required for this landscape report. In a second phase, 20 further interviews were conducted to investigate those thematic areas and to obtain the data required. This two-stage approach was deemed essential to ensure that the research design was both robust and aligned with the current trends and challenges in the field.

2.1.1 PHASE 1: OFF-THE-RECORD INTERVIEWS

In selecting experts to be interviewed, a diversity of expertise and interests was crucial. The 10 interviewees were:

- A specialist from a leading global technology company specialising in visual computing and AI solutions.
- An expert from a prominent open source foundation known for its collaborative projects and initiatives.
- An authority from an international consortium dedicated to ensuring the open development and evolution of standards.
- A professional from a multinational technology company with a history in computer hardware, software, and services.
- An expert from a major digital technology association which represents the digital technology industry in Europe.
- An economist specialising in standardisation and software.
- An authority from a project focused on software supply chain standards.
- A professional from a global organisation advocating for open source software and its communities.
- An expert from a small standards consultancy with small and medium-sized software companies as clients.
- A specialist from an initiative dedicated to promoting open standards and practices.

2.1.2 PHASE 2: DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Primary data collection is prioritised for this landscape report. The 20 interviews of the second phase were semi-structured and on-the-record. The duration of each was between half an hour and one hour. They were transcribed and thematically analysed to draw descriptive summaries and develop overarching themes. The selection criteria for our interviewees were based on expertise, geographic representation, and diversity, in order to provide a balanced and informed exploration of the standardisation landscape.

Name	Organisation	Profile
Jimmy Ahlberg	Ericsson	Company Standards Expert
Mirko Boehm	Linux Foundation Europe	Alternative Expert
Silona Bonewald	Leadingbit Solutions LLC	Standards Professional
Deborah Bryant	Independent	Alternative Expert
Jamie Clark	OASIS Open	Standards Professional
Debora Comparin	Thales	Company Standards Expert
Michael Eslamian	Huawei Technologies	Company Standards Expert
Jochen Friedrich	IBM	Company Standards Expert
Ashok Ganesh	CEN-CENELEC	Standards Professional
Chiara Giovannini	ANEC	Standards Professional
Daniel Haack	DIN - German Institute for Standardisation	Standards Professional
Kai Jakobs	RWTH Aachen	Alternative Expert
Théo Jaekel	Independent Expert (Standards and Human Rights)	Company Standards Expert
Konstantinos Karachalios	IEEE	Standards Professional
Mallory Knodel	The Center for Democracy and Technology (CDT)	Emerging Technology Expert
Tobie Langel	UnlockOpen	Alternative Expert
Arnaud Le Hors	IBM	Company Standards Expert
Alexander Prenter	Fair Standards Alliance (FSA)	Company Standards Expert
Dirk-Willem van Gulik	Apache Software Foundation (ASF)	Alternative Expert
Dirk Weiler	Nokia/ETSI (Retired at time of publication)	Company Standards Expert

2.3 Limitations and Implications

This study employed primarily qualitative research methods, which inherently come with certain limitations regarding the generalisability of findings. The qualitative data, derived from a curated selection of interviews, does not represent the entire range of perspectives within the ICT standardisation landscape.

While acknowledging that potential bias is inherent in any qualitative research, this study's interview selection was guided by diverse criteria, including geographic diversity, sector-specific expertise, and gender balance. However, the semi-structured format of the interviews allowed for the emergence of spontaneous themes, prioritising the natural flow of discussion over rigidly structured questioning. This approach inevitably introduces subjectivity, as responses are influenced by the interviewer's interpretations and the interviewees' perspectives.

The final report – and the observations it draws from the interviews conducted – therefore embraces the interpretive validity of findings that stem from an alternative approach to standard

empirical methods. By valuing intuitive insights, subjective perceptions, and conjectural analysis, the research seeks to capture emerging trends and arguments that can complement empirical research. This approach was chosen with the aim of identifying shifts and potential future developments in the ICT standardisation domain.

The selection of interviewees was aimed at being broad to include voices from across the standardisation ecosystem, including standards professionals, company experts, and representatives from academia and civil society. Efforts were also made to ensure diversity in other attributes such as geographic region, industry sector, and demographic background, to capture a wide range of perspectives. However, some gaps may remain due to the inherent limitations of such a sampling process. These gaps may have influenced the findings, but the diversity of insights, including speculative and intuition-based observations, was enriched by the comprehensive inclusion strategy.

Despite the broad selection criteria, the sample lacked regional diversity, with limited representation outside of Europe and North America. Other sectors, such as healthcare, manufacturing, and finance, were not directly included, which could have provided insights into sector-specific standardisation needs. Furthermore, while the sample included representatives from academia and civil society, further inclusion of these groups would have ensured a more comprehensive understanding of societal impacts. Additionally, a greater balance in demographic diversity and representation from governmental agencies could have offered valuable perspectives on regulatory challenges. These gaps may have affected the findings by narrowing the range of viewpoints.

By embracing these methodological choices, the methodology of Phase 2 acknowledges its limitations while also leveraging the unique strengths of qualitative research. It aims to provide a fresh perspective on ICT standardisation, one that is informed by a deeper, albeit possibly speculative, understanding of the underlying trends and future directions. This approach may not eliminate biases but offers a distinct and valuable lens through which to view the evolving standardisation landscape.

In order to address these limitations and enhance the generalisability of our findings, Phase 3a of the study will include a comprehensive stakeholder consultation process. This phase will involve engaging with a broader spectrum of stakeholders to review and refine our initial conclusions and recommendations. Through this consultation, we hope to incorporate a wider array of insights and experiences, thus broadening the applicability and relevance of our research outcomes.

A Note on Terminology in this landscape report

Regulation 1025/2012 clarifies European standardisation terminology by distinguishing “technical specifications” from “standards”, which are exclusively produced by recognised SDOs, ESOs, or EU National Standardization Bodies. Specifications from other sources are not legally defined as “standards” under EU law, despite their common usage and them being commonly referred to as “standards”.

This report focused on the trends driving changes in the “ICT standardisation landscape”. Despite the complexity of this vast and diverse field, a flexible approach to terminology has been employed during both the interview and analysis phases. The report details how the interview data was collected and notes that legal concepts such as “technical specifications” and “standards” are used interchangeably, for example. At points in this landscape report where it is relevant and needed, the difference will be pointed out.

The main reason for this laxness of terminology is that strict adherence to specific terminologies and “getting into the weeds” of the multilayered and complex standardisation landscape may obscure the broader trends and transformations reshaping the standardisation landscape.

For an insightful breakdown of the SDO, ESS, or broader standardisation landscape, and to understand the changes over time, the report’s author referred to *Baron et al. 2023*. The authors describe how the landscape of Standard Development Organisations (SDOs) has evolved from a straightforward hierarchical structure into a dynamic ecosystem.

The transformation into this dynamic ecosystem is marked by the emergence of various new actors, including industry associations and consortia, operating alongside traditional international and regional bodies like ISO, IEC, and ETSI. These entities often vary significantly in their pace, scope, and membership, reflecting rapid technological advancements and the global nature of standardisation efforts. The graphic on the top right outlines this system simply.³

Another example is *Wiegmann et al. 2017*, which highlights the complexity of standardisation in their analysis of the three primary modes – committee-based, market-based, and government-based. Their insights into how these modes interact underscore the necessity of a flexible approach to terminology, aligning with this landscape report’s aim to navigate the inherent complexity of standardisation. The graphic on the bottom right outlines this breakdown.⁴

³ Graphic from Baron, Justus, and Pierre Larouche. “The European Standardisation System at a Crossroads.” Centre on Regulation in Europe (CERRE), May 2023. Available online: [CERRE](#).

⁴ Graphic from Wiegmann et al. 2017: Wiegmann, Paul Moritz, Henk J. de Vries, and Knut Blind. “Multi-mode standardisation: A critical review and a research agenda.” *Research Policy* 46, no. 8 (2017): 1370-1386. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2017.06.002. Available online: [ScienceDirect](#).

CHAPTER 1: THE DRIVERS OF CHANGE IN THE LANDSCAPE

The integration of digital technologies across societal sectors is reshaping social interactions and infrastructures and this, in turn, affects ICT standardisation. There are two secondary drivers of this change: EU regulation and geopolitical competition. EU regulation aims to secure privacy, security, and interoperability, directly influencing the development and adaptation of standards within the regulatory framework. Concurrently, geopolitical competition introduces strategic considerations impacting technology policy and standards, reflecting concerns about national security and economic competitiveness. It is believed that these dynamics will precipitate significant shifts throughout the ICT standardisation system, with new stakeholders entering traditional standards domains because of how they are connected to a piece or a category of software. These new stakeholders are going to demand to be heard and traditional industries and institutions must grapple with those needs; firstly, the new dynamics that come with new participants, and secondly, the central role that software is increasingly occupying in technology and thus in standards development.

C1.1 Primary Driver of Change: Digitisation and Softwarisation of Society

The primary driver of change in the ICT standardisation system, currently, is the digital transformation of society. The evolving nature of standards in response to these changes is highlighted by the majority of experts interviewed for this report. They note software and the internet have led to near-zero transaction costs for collaboration, market aggregations and network effects that simplify interactions but also, at times, centralise control within fewer, larger platform entities.

Some of the interviewees indicated that this might have had broad, abstract impacts on standardisations; for example, that the flexibility of software seems to have led to a decrease in standard complexity and direct applicability, as it was solved and later updated in the reference implementations. That being said, most simply put, the softwarisation of society is most clearly visible in how software is embedded in widely-used products that are in turn interlinked. Or as it has also been put: "Software is eating the world".⁵ This is the reality of the landscape within which ICT standardisation operates.

The Softwarisation of Society

This report will use this concept softwarisation to describe a general trend that emerged from the interviews. It refers to the ongoing process of transformation whereby software plays an increasingly central role in various aspects of daily life and across industries. This process reflects the pervasive integration of software into products, services, and infrastructures, leading to fundamental changes in how society operates. It builds on other trends around the digitisation of processes, the digitalisation of entire industries, the increasing interconnectivity of devices, and the continued reliance of governments and business software-driven solutions to help address complex, society-wide challenges. The softwarisation of society implied a significant shift towards digital transformation and innovation, and has, as this report argues, profound implications for standards development.

These initial reflections hint at this landscape report's concluding discussion around the urgency of adapting standardisation processes for a 'softwarised' society. There have been many calls for change throughout the history of standardisation. In recent decades, these calls have prompted several reforms aimed at either making the system quicker to adapt, more predictive of current and future technologies, more aligned with political objectives, more responsive to industry requirements, or more inclusive.⁶

A recurring theme from the interviews is a shift in perspective from focusing solely on the proliferation of new technology sectors to understanding the impacts of the broader shift of the world increasingly being softwarised. This shift creates new demands for change for the European standardisation system, which was originally designed for a world dominated by physical hardware.

For example, the rapid proliferation of new technologies and standards was noted by industry experts such as Théo Jaekel (independent expert, standardisation and human rights), who

⁵ This has also been framed by this widely-cited article: Andreessen, M. (2011). Why Software is Eating the World. Andreessen Horowitz. Available at: <https://a16z.com/why-software-is-eating-the-world/> [Accessed date: 26 April 2024]

⁶ Baron, Justus, and Pierre Larouche. "The European Standardisation System at a Crossroads." Centre on Regulation in Europe (CERRE), May 2023.

stressed the importance of a unified approach to ensure coherent understanding across different initiatives. Similarly, Miko Boehm of Linux Foundation Europe notes how digitisation is driving change, especially as the processes within standards organisations themselves are not fully digitised, impacting their response capabilities.

While the system has previously addressed software, the continued influence of software across all aspects of society – and the corresponding increase in regulatory scope following new EU regulation – suggest that new approaches might be needed to meet the expectations of new stakeholders and to manage the expanding role of software more effectively. These changes are added on top of other calls for reform for more representation, efficiency and being more in line with European political aims.

Several interviewees pointed to the perceived and real threats posed by lacking cybersecurity and the emergence of artificial intelligence as drivers of regulatory action. This creates new demands and amplifies old pressures on the standardisation system. These technology challenges (and opportunities) and subsequent regulation require functioning standards to safeguard public interests. The lack of historical data on AI and the nature of society's cybersecurity risks, identified as key challenges by some interviewees, could complicate informed decision-making in standardisation, highlighting the need for a new approach to including different stakeholders, and a strategic and swift response to these rapid technological changes.

Reflecting the ICT standardisation sector's response and own evolution, Konstantinos Karachalios of IEEE remarks, "Certain standards are now seen as the foundation for ecosystems, and ecosystems of ecosystems, not just networks, impacting the wellbeing of society as a whole, including the coherence of our democratic institutions and the mental health of the citizens."

Additionally, the expansion of the set of stakeholders that are seen or see themselves as having a role on the standards scene creates even more demands for openness and accessibility of standards and the standards development procedures, which was noted by several interviewees. This increase in potential stakeholders has several consequences at the landscape level, but one worth highlighting is Tobie Langel of UnlockOpen's comment that the influx can challenge traditional validation processes, pushing the boundaries of demands on standardisation to include more strict governance aspects and even abstract concepts such as values, transforming the expected outcomes.

Another consequence of more software is that there is more open source, which is a form of collaborative innovation similar yet different to standardisation.⁷ Daniel Haack of the German Institute for Standardisation (DIN) points out both the broadening of stakeholders in standardisation and open source and hints at how this can be interlinked: "Digitisation is transforming industries that traditionally didn't engage with open source, which are now becoming essential for meeting the evolving demands of industry. In this context, our goal must be to continuously increase trust in open source solutions and reduce reservations to enable widespread digitisation." This will be a central theme of the impacts in the ICT standardisation landscape in this report, as it is a clear example of a broad change brought forth by the softwarisation of society.

C1.2 Secondary Drivers of Change: Regulation

⁷ Biddle, C. Bradford. (2019). Linux Foundation is Eating the World. *Journal of Open Law, Technology & Society*, 11(1), pp. 57–74. DOI: 105033/jolts.v11i1.137.

and Geopolitical Rivalries

■ C1.2.1 REGULATION OF THE DIGITAL MARKETS

It is not surprising that there is near-consensus among the interviewees that the regulation of digital markets in the European Union (EU) significantly influences the ICT standardisation landscape. EU regulation aims to achieve political goals such as fair competition, privacy, security, and interoperability but it also sets the framework for the economic activities of all stakeholders relevant to standardisation (and stakeholders in general). Regulation 1025/2012 is the framework that creates the direct links, as EU regulation can include direct requests from the European Commission for harmonised standards from the European Standards Organisations.⁸

A central element to the framework linking regulation, standardisation and the practices of societal stakeholders is the “presumption of conformity”. This legal concept implies that products conforming to EU harmonised standards benefit from a legal presumption that they meet the essential requirements of the relevant EU legislation. Such presumption facilitates the free movement of goods within the European Single Market by simplifying compliance processes for manufacturers and reducing the need for additional conformity assessments.⁹

It is through this mechanism recent EU legislative measures such as the Digital Markets Act (DMA), Digital Services Act (DSA), EU Cyber Resilience Act (CRA), Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act), and Data Act further extend the regulatory scope into the realm of software, albeit in different ways. Later chapters of this report will discuss the potential impacts of the rapid increase in requests for software-related standards.

Another impact of this regulatory change is the proliferation of new stakeholders in the ICT standardisation landscape. They come from the until-now unregulated software realms being directly or indirectly affected by EU regulation, and thus wanting the presumption of conformity that the future harmonised standards will provide.¹⁰ These include, for example, small and medium-sized and micro software companies, code-hosting platforms, software foundations and sometimes even individual developers, that make up the bulk of code-production in Europe.¹¹

In addition to the demands in recent EU legislation for harmonised standards, there are specific regulations and policies that more directly affect the workings of the standards system itself. These include the already mentioned Regulation 1025/2012,¹² which lays the legal foundation

⁸ A harmonised standard is a European standard developed by one of the recognised European Standards Organisations: CEN, CENELEC, or ETSI. It's created following a request from the European Commission. These standards are used by manufacturers, other economic operators, or conformity assessment bodies to demonstrate that their products, services, or processes comply with relevant EU legislation. See more: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/european-standards/harmonised-standards_en

⁹ European Commission. (n.d.). Conformity assessment. Your Europe. Retrieved April 26, 2024, from https://europa.eu/youreurope/business/product-requirements/compliance/conformity-assessment/index_en.htm

¹⁰ Note that the use of harmonised standards is voluntary, but often wanted.

¹¹ Blind, K., Böhm, M., Grzegorzewska, P., Katz, A., Muto, S., Pätsch, S., & Schubert, T. (2021). The impact of Open Source Software and Hardware on technological independence, competitiveness and innovation in the EU economy: Final Study Report. Brussels: European Commission.

¹² European Union. (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on European standardisation, amending Council Directives 89/686/EEC and 93/15/EEC and Directives 94/9/EC, 94/25/EC, 95/16/EC, 97/23/EC, 98/34/EC, 2004/22/EC, 2007/23/EC, 2009/23/EC and

for the European standardisation system, as well as the New Legislative Framework (NLF),¹³ antitrust policy such as the Horizontal Guidelines,¹⁴ and various intellectual property regulations and guidelines such as the Standard Essential Patents (SEPs) framework¹⁵ and the Intellectual Property Rights Enforcement Directive (IPRED).¹⁶

These pieces of policy provide the legal framework for the collaborative work between organisations in standards bodies. Several of these documents are at the time of writing either in review or up for review.

■ C1.2.2 THE INFLUENCE OF GEOPOLITICS

Unsurprisingly, there was general agreement among the interviewees that geopolitical dynamics significantly drive change in the ICT standardisation landscape, with strategic competition among global powers driving new demands for technology policy and standards. This influence has increased following more pronounced rivalries in recent years, particularly following the rise of China. While not the main focus of this landscape report, geopolitical dynamics are an important driver of change and behaviour in the ICT standardisation landscape and it has been covered extensively in scholarly research.¹⁷

An aspect of this relevant to several comments made by interviewees is that for decades, European, Japanese, and American entities have predominantly led the international standardisation landscape, with other players joining SSOs later and sporadically. Chinese organisations, deemed as “latecomers”, face acceptance challenges in international ICT standardisation. This is at times expressed as political friction in the ICT standardisation landscape.¹⁸ An example of how this friction is expressed is how, while Western entities continue to hold a majority share of leadership roles within SDOs, there is now more competition for these roles from said “latecomers”.¹⁹

2009/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Council Decision 87/95/EEC and Decision No 1673/2006/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council. Official Journal of the European Union, L 316/12.

¹³ European Commission. The New Legislative Framework for the Marketing of Products. Retrieved from https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/goods/new-legislative-framework_en

¹⁴ European Commission. (2023). Press release: Antitrust: Commission adopts new Horizontal Block Exemption Regulations and Horizontal Guidelines. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_2990

¹⁵ European Commission. Standard Essential Patents. Retrieved from https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/strategy/intellectual-property/patent-protection-eu/standard-essential-patents_en

¹⁶ EUR-Lex. (2004). Directive 2004/48/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights (Text with EEA relevance). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32004L0048R%2801%29>

¹⁷ For example Mattli, W., & Büthe, T. (2011). *The New Global Rulers: The Privatization of Regulation in the World Economy*. Princeton University Press; Baron, J., & Kanevskaia, O. (2021). *Global Competition for Leadership Positions in Standards Development Organizations*. Northwestern University and KU Leuven; Baron, Justus, and Pierre Larouche (2023). *The European Standardisation System at a Crossroads*. Centre on Regulation in Europe (CERRE), May 2023. Available online: [CERRE](https://cerre.eu).

¹⁸ Schott, L., & Schaefer, K.J. (2023). Acceptance of Chinese latecomers' technological contributions in international ICT standardization — The role of origin, experience, and collaboration. *Research Policy*, 52(2023), 104656. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2022.104656

¹⁹ Baron, J., & Kanevskaia, O. (2021). *Global Competition for Leadership Positions in Standards Development Organizations*. Northwestern University and KU Leuven.

Regarding Europe and the EU, the pursuit of digital sovereignty has emerged as a prominent theme as a driver of change in ICT standardisation. While there is less agreement among the interviewees on how much change has actually occurred, there is consensus that political rhetoric reflects the continent's ambition to assert greater control over its digital future. Notable examples illustrating this drive include the 2022 Standardisation Strategy, the establishment of the High-Level Forum on European Standardisation²⁰ (HLF) as aimed at enhancing strategic coordination, and attempts to coordinate international positioning to strengthen Europe's role in global standardisation discussions. Moreover, following the so-called James Elliott case, the Commission is seen as aiming to enhance its supervision of European standards that underpin EU legislation.²¹

In the United States, a development that was raised by several interviewees as noteworthy in this space was the relatively recent publication of a first national standardisation strategy.²² It is formulated to address evolving technological landscapes and global competition. This strategy aims to strengthen, on one hand, America's position in emerging technologies while also promoting, on the other hand, traditional standardisation goals, such as interoperability and global cooperation in standardisation efforts.

The overarching take-away from the interviews that commented on this trend is that the future of global standards is under strain from geopolitical pressure. That said, it remains to be seen what challenges will arise in trying to reconcile different regions' political goals, or which will be given priority if a choice has to be made. Interoperability and streamlined market access clash with diverse demands on standards to accommodate varying regional technological preferences, values and hard national strategy goals.

It is also worth noting, however, that the tensions between global standardisation and regional preferences are not new. Agreements such as the *Vienna Agreement*, signed between CEN and ISO in 1991, which recognises the primacy of international standards²³, and the *Frankfurt Agreement*, inked during the annual IEC General Meeting in October 2016, between the IEC and CENELEC to enhance harmonisation between International and European standards,²⁴ demonstrate a longstanding effort to reconcile international and European standards for decades. Many interviewees do indicate that there is a perceived risk of a future of reverting back to fragmentation.

²⁰ High-Level Forum on European Standardisation. "What is the High-Level Forum on European Standardisation?" European Commission. https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/european-standards/standardisation-policy/high-level-forum-european-standardisation_en, Accessed 3 May 2024.

²¹ Baron, Justus, and Pierre Larouche (2023). *The European Standardisation System at a Crossroads*. Centre on Regulation in Europe (CERRE), May 2023. Available online: [CERRE](https://cerre.eu).

²² U.S. Government. (2023). *National Standards Strategy 2023*. The White House. Available at: <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/US-Gov-National-Standards-Strategy-2023.pdf>

²³ CEN-CENELEC. "CEN Cooperation with ISO." CEN-CENELEC, <https://www.cencenelec.eu/about-cen/cen-and-iso-cooperation/>. Accessed 3 May 2024.

²⁴ CEN-CENELEC. "CENELEC Cooperation with IEC." CENELEC, <https://www.cencenelec.eu/about-cenelec/cenelec-and-iec-cooperation/>. Accessed 3 May 2024.

C1.3 Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape

With the digitisation and softwarisation of society as a primary driver of change, and regulation and geopolitical rivalries as secondary drivers of change, this report will in the following chapters present diverse views of how this is expressed as impacts and trends in the ICT standardisation landscape. Grounded in insights gleaned from 30 interviews, it aims to paint a broad picture of the diverse reactions and responses to the changes and impacts from stakeholders within this ecosystem.

With its methodology and analyses, these chapters provide an intellectual foundation for teasing out preliminary conclusions from the complex interplay between societal, regulatory, technological, economic, and geopolitical factors shaping the ICT standardisation landscape, and Europe's place in it.

CHAPTER 2: THE REGULATION OF DIGITAL MARKETS

The regulation of digital markets is significantly reshaping and expanding the landscape of ICT standardisation. Some of the new regulation comes as a result of concentration of market power in the hands of a few major technology companies, as well as demand for more trust, safety and security for consumers and users in the digital markets. The regulation influences many things, including innovation, market entry, and the development and adoption of standards. It is noted that market leaders seem to strategically avoid leading standardisation efforts in domains they dominate. Their lack of participation in standardisation creates barriers for others, potentially fragmenting the market and slowing down the standardisation of new technology areas.

C2.1 Market Concentration and Standardisation

The concentration of market power in the hands of a few major technology companies is important in terms of understanding the current state of and trends in ICT standardisation, several of the interviewees pointed out. This dynamic – characterised by strategic manoeuvring of market leaders and market challengers' reactions to it – has implications for innovation, market entry, and the development and adoption of standards.

Before going into the direct effects of EU regulation on the ICT standardisation landscape, this section covers the interviewees view of the state of the ICT markets, and how market concentration, which is a source of some of the EU Regulation, also has direct implications for the day-to-day work in standardisation.

At times, strategic avoidance by market leaders to lead standardisation efforts in domains they dominate has been particularly notable. As Arnaud Le Hors of IBM points out: "... the market leader is seldom the one to lead the charge in areas where they dominate". This scenario fosters an environment where other players rally around standardisation efforts as a means to challenge the market leader's dominance. The willingness to standardise diminishes when companies can push their proprietary solutions without collaboration, thus creating a possibility to erect barriers for others to enter the market.

The dynamics of network effects is especially pronounced in the software and platform sectors, where network effects amplify the value of a single dominant platform over competing ones. Dirk-Willem van Gulik of the Apache Software Foundation provides an illustration of these market dynamics: "There can only be one biggest auction house. In a friction-free market, the second biggest auction house is significantly smaller, and others don't count much." He also notes how, "...technological bloat and market concentration mean that only a few places like Microsoft DevOps or GitHub can run significant software pipelines, limiting standards diversity and increasing dependency on major players."

Mirko Boehm of the Linux Foundation EU clarifies the dual nature of large companies' motivations regarding standardisation. Initially, there may be an interest in interoperability to gain market traction; however, as market dominance is secured, the inclination shifts towards proprietary or closed protocols. He states, "initially, there was an inclination towards interoperability, but as they grew larger or sought to control the market, their focus shifted towards exclusivity." This reflects a broader trend where market dominance influences standardisation more than the actual development of standards itself.

Konstantinos Karachalios of IEEE also reflects on these implications for standardisation: "Large corporations, by virtue of their size, are able to create de facto standards, and can afford to bypass participation in open standardisation processes. This significant de facto power is problematic, not just economically; it also causes broader societal impacts, through monopolistic practices by large infrastructures" Looking to the practices that this market concentration and lack of open standardisation processes enables, Mr. Karachalios sees a link "even to damaging effects on childhood".

Mallory Knodel of CDT captures another layer of the relationship between market concentration, competition and standardisation processes: "Large companies like Google expand the commons through open standards only to later dominate them." This also illustrates that while interoperable, open standards are critical for initial success, they do not necessarily benefit from long-term support from the companies which benefited from them. On the contrary,

open standards can benefit companies who will later try to undermine those very standards, as they are enablers of competition.

Boehm addresses that this cannot be generalised to all situations, and that standardisation has strategic value also for market leaders at times, depending on how the market is defined and the nature of the industry. Looking in particular to telecommunications, Boehm states: "We have seen that, in Europe, it is easier for large businesses, as opposed to small and medium-sized enterprises, to engage in standards development. However, private organisations like ETSI primarily serve the interests of their member companies, not the public interest in the development of effective standards."

Mr. Clark of OASIS Open highlights that standardisation, if successful, can at the same time mitigate these issues: "Market concentration issues are addressed in standards and open source environments by ensuring that processes allow for new entrants, as well as incumbents and competitors, maintaining competition and preventing monopolistic practices by requiring interoperability." Similarly, Mr. Langel remarks on the manipulation by large corporations in certain markets: "Incumbents benefit from a lack of standardisation. It makes their solution the default 'standard'. This reduces portability and interoperability, creates vendor lock-in, and hurts competition. The more concentrated the market, the worse it gets. This is true in cloud as it is in social networks or messaging apps."

Parts of the drive behind new regulation is the political awareness of the risks and problems following the concentration in digital markets. This, too, has a link to governance: as noted by Le Hors, the emphasis on open governance and standards serves as a counterbalance to market concentration, suggesting a strategic approach to fostering competition. This perspective is echoed by Debora Comparin of Thales, who highlights the potential of regulation to ignite more dynamic market activities by challenging the closed ecosystems of dominant market players.

Concerns were also raised about potential barriers for smaller entities, where the complexity and cost of compliance could hinder market entry. Knodel shares this concern, highlighting the bureaucratic nature of using standards as a prerequisite for market entry, which can detract from their original purpose of fostering innovation and interoperability.

Amid these concerns, Mr. Haack of DIN offers a contrasting perspective from a national standards body pointing to the role of governance of SDOs: "Despite the influence of large companies, or 'hyperscalers', in many sectors, their impact on standardisation is limited by the consensus-based processes, our approach to integrate experts from all stakeholder groups, and the structure of standardisation activities in general. Arbitration procedures secure the rights of minority interests."

The interviews underscore that the ICT standardisation landscape is directly affected by the presence of dominant players. And while pro-competitive, governance-focused regulation and policy is generally seen as in the interest of challengers. However, other interviewees suggest that regulatory interventions have complex ramifications, and while the regulation might be a reaction to market concentration, those reactions can lead to market incumbents' positions being further strengthened, if not done right.

C2.2 Standardisation and the EU's Regulation of Software

The interviewees generally agree that the European Union's regulatory response to the aforementioned complexities is to try to strike a delicate balance between fostering innovation, ensuring fair competition, and protecting consumer interests. EU legislation is becoming increasingly detailed and technical in its scope, which could be seen as a result of the legislators' wish to address these dilemmas.

Regulation 1025/2012 has been pivotal in recognising and empowering standards organisations to develop necessary harmonised European standards that support regulatory objectives. As a general point, Jochen Friedrich of IBM observes, "European regulation plays a pivotal role in shaping trustworthiness through standardisation." What is novel, according to several interviewees, is that emerging sectors like artificial intelligence and software-specific challenges like cybersecurity, where an extensive list of standards are requested under the AI Act and the CRA, are examples of how the regulatory framework built for a world of hardware now extends into software. Tobie Langel notes the link with standardisation, as there is an increasing reliance on standards for legislative implementation: "legislation increasingly relies on standards for implementation, and I would highlight cyber security concerns as a key driver of legislative actions."

This does not necessarily mean that all digital market regulation is software regulation. Michael Eslamian of Huawei Technologies points out the specific aims of recent regulatory acts: "the Digital Markets Act and Digital Services Act are regulatory acts aimed at reducing market dominance of few and ensuring fair competition and improving possibilities for consumers, they are not primarily about creating standardisation. The AI Act, Data Act, CRA and others are however generating standardisation requests."

While there's an increasing reliance on standards for legislative implementation, it's important to distinguish between regulatory acts aimed at reducing market dominance and ensuring fair competition, such as the DMA, Data Act and DSA, and those primarily focused on security and safety, which tend to generate more standardisation requests relevant for software stakeholders, like the AI Act and CRA. That said, also the DMA and Data Act have standardisation implications around interoperability as a pro-competitive tool.

Another point that arguably is linked to regulation extending into the software realm is that there is broad agreement that regulators today seem to favour more prescriptive and technically detailed regulations. This is, according to some of the interviewees, a result of trying to technocratically solve difficulties stemming from regulation further extending into software, relying on a standardisation system built for hardware.

C2.3 Software Regulation and Demand for New Harmonised Standards

As a result of the NLF and a sense of political urgency, the adoption of legislation over recent years was swift. It is now imposing significant demands on standardisation efforts, placing strain on the capabilities of ESOs. A concrete example of this strain can be seen in the RED Delegated Act, which has compelled CEN-CENELEC Joint Technical Committee 13 Working

Group 8 to postpone the delivery of standards by a year.²⁵ These delays might foreshadow the challenges faced by ESOs in keeping up with the need for standards development amidst the rapid legislative changes.

Demands for speed from the ESOs is also nothing new. In fact, as Baron and Larouche point out, the system in place today is there because demands for speed in the past. During the 1970s, the harmonisation of technical norms was widely regarded as unsuccessful. The legislative process for standardisation was slow-moving, hindering progress. Recognising the need for improvement, a shift towards a more efficient use of standardisation was sought.

In the early 1990s, the European Commission proposed the centralised European standardisation system we have today as a solution to the perceived sluggishness in standard development within organisations like CEN and CENELEC. One key proposal involved the establishment of sectoral standards bodies to allow for greater stakeholder representation and potentially expedite the process. This reorganisation was exemplified by the creation of ETSI as a third ESO. However, the Commission's suggestion to form additional sectoral ESOs met widespread opposition from stakeholders and was ultimately abandoned.²⁶

Commenting on the present day and future trends, many interviewees say one of the most important drivers of change is the extension of regulation and subsequent harmonised standards into the realm of software.

The speed of regulation is also something touched by the experts interviewed. As noted by Comparin, "... regulations are coming faster in the market than before", indicating a shift towards a regulatory environment where legal frameworks dictate the pace of change and demand on the system to produce standards in rapidly changing technology areas, which in turn also increases the demand pressure: the new EU regulation is asking for a record number of harmonised standards, that meet political requirements and at record speed.

In this context, Kai Jakobs of RWTH Aachen raises concerns: "The emphasis on speed in standardisation needs to be balanced with the necessity to get it right, especially for standards that have significant societal or ecological impacts." He is not the only one concerned with the quality needing to be assured. For example, Jochen Friedrich of IBM highlights the need for pragmatic approaches in standards: "Europe needs standards that are simple, clear, and implementable without compromising quality, focusing on incremental improvement."

Another macro-trend indicated by the experts is that the regulations create a shift towards compliance-related standards, which focus on safety, security, and other regulatory requirements. This is the nature of for example the AI Act and the CRA. Interviewees speculate that this could come at the expense of standards that deliver interoperability, and by extension open markets, incentives to innovate and competition in a system that is already under strain. This sentiment is for example expressed by Ms. Knodel, who contrasts the innovative potential of open voluntary standards with the checkbox mentality often associated with regulatory compliance: "Regulatory-driven standardisation tends to stifle innovation by promoting a compliance-first mentality that often shortchanges the potential for consensus-driven technological advancement."

²⁵ Kiwa. (2023, July 31). Radio Equipment Directive (RED) Application Date Postponed. Retrieved from <https://www.kiwa.com/en/media/news/2023/red-application-date-postponed/>

²⁶ Baron, Justus, and Pierre Larouche. "The European Standardisation System at a Crossroads." Centre on Regulation in Europe (CERRE), May 2023. Available online: [CERRE](https://cerre.eu).

On the other hand, Silona Bonewald of LeadingBit criticises this trend, advocating for a broader emphasis on production readiness and quality over mere compliance: “The current regulatory approach often favours compliance at the expense of fostering genuine innovation and quality in production.” Chiara Giovannini of ANEC presents a general counterpoint to this, however, suggesting that the dichotomy between compliance and interoperability is false: “Standards development can address a spectrum of requirements effectively without neglecting interoperability. It is possible to craft regulations that do not stifle innovation but rather encourage it within a safe and fair framework.”

The broad conclusion that can be drawn from the interviews is that the extension of regulatory frameworks to encompass software brings new and complex demands to an already strained European standardisation system. These new demands include the rapid development of harmonised standards that address the intricacies of software, the new software stakeholders that will demand to be heard in the process, while ensuring that these standards align with both technical and political expectations at record speed. This compounds existing pressures for standards that ensure safety, inclusiveness, security, interoperability, and compliance across various sectors.

C2.4 The Challenge for the ESOs

A majority of the interviews focused on the ESOs and their capacity to meet the challenge that is the increased demands that are being put on them. Looking more to the policies related to standardisation itself, Regulation 1025/2012 stands out, and this will be revisited later in the paper. The challenge is for standards bodies, in particular the ESOs responding directly to regulation, to meet this demand while navigating industry preferences, political goals and requests for inclusivity from new stakeholders. As noted by Ashok Ganesh of CEN-CENELEC, “European standardisation bodies have opportunities increasingly to address European strategic interests, particularly in response to global technological leadership challenges. But, at the end of the day the content of any standards will continue to be defined by industry experts”

The interviewees are torn regarding what change is needed in the ESOs and Regulation 1025/2012, which in turn signals the many demands. On the one hand, Professor Jakobs of RWTH Aachen raises general concerns: “Policy makers should not interfere at a detailed level in standardisation processes. Their strategic influence is understandable, but direct interference, such as financial threats to enforce compliance, is deeply concerning.” But the strategic role of standardisation drives interest for reform. As van Gulik of ASF notes, though: “As technology evolves, the rules of the game are being rewritten by global players, prompting a need for Europe to reassess and potentially adjust its regulatory frameworks to remain competitive”, foreshadowing the next chapter.

Amid the shifts driven by regulation in the ICT standardisation landscape, it is clear that new, sometimes conflicting, demands for reform of the ESS and ESOs are emerging. Most of the demands are not new, but some are made by new-ish stakeholders. There is agreement that a balance must be struck between promoting compliance and fostering innovation — but where that balance lies there is less agreement on.

The increasing inclination towards prescriptive regulations that emphasise safety, security, and other regulatory demands risks, according to some interviewees, overshadowing the need for standards that ensure interoperability, thereby supporting open markets and encouraging competition. Yet, as suggested by Giovannini, it is perhaps entirely feasible to develop

regulations that both safeguard public interests and foster innovation within a robust and equitable framework. Regardless, the demand for more and higher quality standards has drastically increased and changed shape following the wave of regulation of the past years.

CHAPTER 3: GEOPOLITICAL RIVALRIES AND STANDARDISATION

This chapter gathers the comments from the interviewees on how geopolitical rivalries are a significant factor impacting Europe's stance and strategies within the global ICT standardisation arena. Europe faces challenges in navigating and asserting its influence amidst these forces, which in turn add to the pressures on the European standardisation system, and complicate the landscape for European actors. More is again demanded from standardisation. Interviewees underscore the necessity of maintaining a balance in politicising standards, promoting specific values and ensuring its digital sovereignty while avoiding triggering conflict and fragmentation.

C3.1 ICT Standardisation in a Geopolitical Landscape

As touched on in Chapter 1, the competition for influence in ICT standardisation has intensified, showcasing geopolitical rivalries, particularly between Europe, the United States, and China. Market strategies, political manoeuvring, and the pursuit of technological influence drive the dynamics of the landscape.

Clark of OASIS Open points to the broader geopolitical implications: “The geopolitical aspect of standardisation is evident as concentrations of entities from various nations, including Germany in data protection, China in telecommunications, and the US in cloud computing, contribute to global standards, which then impacts local technological policies.” Alexander Prenter of the Fair Standards Alliance’s observation indicates a clear interplay: “There is a perception that the increasing involvement of Asian companies in standardisation has turned it into a political issue, leading to national interests influencing standardisation processes.” As pointed out by Professor Jakobs, this has led to reactions in Europe: “The European Commission’s recent approach to standardisation is politically motivated, inspired by global competitors like China using standards as geopolitical tools.”

C3.2 Implications of the EU’s Standardisation Strategy

These tensions reflect not just market competition but a deeper, strategic contest over influence and dominance in the ICT sector. Europe finds itself in a challenging position, striving to navigate and assert its influence amidst the predominant forces of the US and China. One of the more concrete ways this has been expressed is in the EU Strategy on Standardisation from early 2022, where the Commission wants standards “to foster EU values, policy objectives and regulatory implementation”²⁷.

The interviewees who commented directly on the standardisation strategy were generally appreciating the goals, while also being quick in pointing out trade-offs and dilemmas.

Accelerating standards development to meet the rapid pace of technological development may conflict with maintaining quality standards outputs. This demand for speed might in turn reduce stakeholder engagement and oversight. From a more geopolitical perspective, the push for technological sovereignty can clash with the necessity for international cooperation, particularly when global interoperability is essential. Balancing global leadership and market fairness can also pose challenges, as asserting EU values in international standards may lead to trade policy conflicts with partners that don’t share the same standards and priorities, potentially creating friction in global trade relationships.

A recurrent point in the interviews was the reference to values in the context of standardisation. Mr. Weiler of Nokia states that “We must also be cautious with the idea that standards convey

²⁷ European Commission. (2022). An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green, and digital EU single market. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions, COM(2022) 31 final.

values, which is now a concept strongly promoted by the Commission. Most technical standards are value-neutral because they are simply technical specifications that implement specific technologies.” Mr. Friedrich of IBM comments on the approach Europe should take: “The issue of values and standards needs a considerate approach. We should not overload technical standards with values, but we must ensure that standards do not violate European values.”

The pursuit of global standards is a key strategic objective for Europe in its strategy. Industry representatives generally support this goal, but are concerned about the current trends. Mr. Ahlberg of Ericsson, “I sort of came into this with truly global standards and now I’m starting to see a convergence or divergence into various pushes for regional standards” and “if we consider the goal of a standard to be global, which is where you would have the true benefits of it, I find it to be kind of disheartening if we went back to where we were a long time ago, like 20, 25 years ago, way before I got started in standards.”

Ms. Comparin of Thales notes that “There is regional economic competition that defines standards. There are two very large blocks: the US and the Asian block, and then there is Europe”. This “size difference” underscores the challenges Europe faces in driving change at a global level, and that there are risks of isolation if European interests are prioritised strongly. Most of the interviewees believe that Europe’s ambitions, however defined, are expected to be contested, which risks the future of global standards in some technology areas. Professor Jakobs comments on this: “The fragmentation due to legal and regional interests is likely to worsen, making cooperation difficult. Europe’s strategy appears increasingly focused on regional interests, potentially leading to a ‘fortress Europe’ scenario.”

Mr. Weiler articulates his concern: “The danger is clearly that by defining these technologies, these topics, as critical to Europe... the obvious consequence would be that we will not agree on global standards anymore and therefore lose the benefits of global standards”. Mr. Jaekel adds, “There is a concern that we’re moving into a more divided ICT global space, where...the European Union and the US are regulating...while other parts of the world, led by China, have a very different approach.”

That said, this view can be further complemented by Mr. Clark of OASIS Open’s view, which suggests that European regulation has global effects, and that it goes beyond just technical merits to also include broader socio-economic impacts. He highlights Europe’s standardising influence globally, noting, “Europe’s ability to influence global digital standards, expanding from akin to the GDPR into software and digital services liability, positions it to define rules that could shape even more behaviours in the global digital market”.

There is a point to consider regarding the increasing role of software in society. Although not extensively detailed, a few interviewees highlighted the challenges that software faces in regulation and standardisation, particularly in a world marked by heightened geopolitical rivalries. Historically, technological innovation in hardware began regionally and then achieved global interoperability and presence, partly through standardisation. In contrast, software “started globally” and is now being asked to meet regional regulatory demands. Since software development already has a global focus, tension arises when regional regulations—and thus standards—require adjustments to universally designed products.

Mr. Le Hors of IBM shares his view as a representative of an American software company acting globally: “We’re keen to establish global standards to avoid creating different product versions for different regions. We aim for global consistency, not to spread US standards specifically. I’m observing a trend, based mostly on discussions and not on solid data, that

Europe sees this as a chance to set standards for everyone else. I wonder if that's the best approach."

The integration of contributions from Chinese "latecomers" into the standardisation process is generally seen by interviewees and scholarly research as the source of tension in the standardisation space. But this is a view that requires nuance. For example, Mr. Karachalios of IEEE reflects on this interaction and how the quality of technical contributions to standards is still the central way to participate: "Engagement with China by IEEE led to positive contributions in standard development, showing benefits of cooperative international relationships despite geopolitical tensions."

The pressure on ESOs and the European Standardisation System to align with strategic interests is significant, particularly concerning internal governance and leadership. Reflecting on the European Commission's current trajectory regarding SDO leadership, Jimmy Ahlberg of Ericsson remarked, "The changing landscape seems to favour CEN-CENELEC as a more 'European' standards body." Other interviewees highlighted broader policy concerns and pressures. Mr. Clark noted that, "Some global standards may embed the policy values of a region or a marketplace, resulting in their reassessment for suitability within the European ecosystem." Mr. Ganesh of CEN-CENELEC added, "Standardisation efforts are increasingly influenced by geopolitical dynamics – leading the standards setting can give advantages so there is heightened interest in bringing proposals for addressing new technologies – or other key areas like critical materials - to the standards bodies."

Influence is not just counted in leadership roles but in terms of numbers of engineers contributing. Mr. Ahlberg of Ericsson points out that "Asian companies being some of the largest contributors, brings many engineers to standards bodies, which isn't a bad thing since their involvement helps get the work done, and create global standards with global buy-in." For telecommunications, standardisation cannot be seen as a solely European initiative in his view: "While it might seem at first glance that only European standards bodies are involved, the actual support, in terms of manpower, comes from a broader international spectrum."

Beyond manpower and leadership roles, there is influence in terms of patents as well. This has particular bearing in telecommunications standards. Mr. Prenter remarks, "The influence of Chinese companies in standardisation has significantly increased, especially in 5G, where they hold a large portion of patents," revealing the strategic implications of patent control. While not the main focus on this landscape report, the role of patents and IPR policies will be touched upon in the next chapter.

From the interviews, it is clear that experts in the landscape have the perception that the EU is trying to leverage standardisation in its pursuit of digital sovereignty. This, however, is seen as a dual-edged sword that can lead to regional isolation. As highlighted by Mr. Le Hors, "the pursuit of digital sovereignty might inadvertently lead to a more fragmented digital environment." Mr. Ahlberg of Ericsson articulates that he has observed a shift in perspective, suggesting that "the existing rules [for standardisation], once beneficial to Europe, are now perceived as less advantageous," while underscoring that he makes no judgement on if the "rules" are more or less beneficial to Europe.

A point that was raised by several interviewees was the perceived one-sidedness of the digital sovereignty and standardisation discussions in policy circles. The omission that was pointed to was open source, as another form of technical collaboration closely linked to digital sovereignty aspirations. Mr. Friedrich of IBM asserts that, "There is an opportunity and a need to discuss more with the European Commission how open source and standardisation contribute to digital sovereignty." The urgency to get this right is supported by Professor

Jakobs: "Europe must proactively engage in both standardisation and open source to maintain digital sovereignty. Current strategies seem more focused on standards, but the balance may shift towards open source in response to global trends."

The general conclusion from the interviews is that the potential risks of fragmentation looms large. Earlier chapters outlined the strain created by strategic corporate decisions, but it is also fueled by regional ambitions and geopolitical influences. A recurrent theme among the interviewees is to not under-appreciate the value of the global interoperability that global standards bring, which in turn is important for the continued advancement of ICT technologies.

Looking to the next chapter, the nature of the technologies that are being standardised is at the same time shifting following the softwarisation of society and the subsequent regulation and standardisation of software. This brings additional demands for speed, reform, and inclusivity. An area where this is particularly pronounced, according to several interviewees for this landscape report, is how regulation and standardisation now will interact with open source. This lays bare many of the challenges inherent to the European Standardisation strategy, but possibly also opportunities for how to achieve the sometimes clashing goals of the EU.

CHAPTER 4: OLD AND NEW STRAINS ON THE EUROPEAN STANDARDISATION SYSTEM

Where the softwarisation of society introduces new demands in the ICT standardisation landscape, EU regulation of digital markets increases the demand for harmonised standards and geopolitics brings demands both on the governance of standards bodies and the standards being developed to help achieve regional political goals. This chapter focuses on the interviewees' comments on the old and new demands for change and reform in the standardisation system. It also highlights how the dynamics of the landscape lead to new pressures to change at the core and at the margin of the ICT standardisation system. There is a particular focus on the convergence of open source and standardisation, noting the significant impact of open source on the standardisation process and vice versa. But the pressure to include diverse stakeholders into the standard-setting process goes beyond open source, and arguably the frictions of the shift towards more collaborative and inclusive standardisation practices are intensifying. Representation and efficacy are, as always, competing demands.

C4.1 Demands for Inclusivity and Diversity in Standardisation

Demands for increasing the inclusivity of the European standardisation system is nothing new. In recent years, several different policy papers and documents have called for just this, demanding representation beyond the industry players and national bodies already established in the ESOs. The stakeholder groups that demand attention are diverse, for example:

- **European Parliament Resolution (2023):** The European Parliament's 2023 resolution on the "Standardisation strategy for the single market" calls for a greater focus on SMEs in ESO governance and emphasises the importance of broader stakeholder representation in EU standardisation efforts.²⁸
- **Environmental Coalition on Standards (2022):** ECOS, alongside ANEC, ETUC, and SBS, emphasises the need for a standardisation system that includes diverse voices, especially those focused on environmental sustainability and social equity. They advocate modernising the standardisation system to align with EU public interests, including the goals of the European Green Deal.²⁹
- **European Commission Standardisation Strategy (2022):** The European Union's Standardisation Strategy emphasises the importance of enhancing inclusivity, transparency, and openness in the standard-setting process. It recognizes the demands on the ESOs to address representation imbalances by involving SMEs, civil society, and users more actively. But it also adds a demand of increasing government representation in standardisation governance, by giving national standardisation bodies in the EU and EEA decision-making power during the development of Commission-requested standards.³⁰

More generally, it's worth noting the role of Annex III organisations, as outlined in Regulation 1025/2012. Measures to enhance inclusivity exist in theory, the real question is whether they are sufficient. According to Professor Jakobs of RWTH Aachen, "While there is an intention to include more societal stakeholders in standardisation, current efforts seem insufficient. Umbrella organisations may not adequately represent the diversity within their constituencies, raising concerns about the inclusivity of the standardisation process."

Previous chapters have outlined how new regulation and geopolitical rivalries expands the number and diversity of stakeholder groups in the ICT standardisation landscape. The interviews suggest that there is an increasing number of demands put on the ESOs, and that these demands often are competing, putting strain on the European standardisation system. This is, as stated nothing, new and has been covered extensively in research.

²⁸ European Parliament. "REPORT on a standardisation strategy for the single market." Committee on the Internal Market and Consumer Protection. Rapporteur: Adam Bielan. Procedure: 2022/2058(INI). A9-0136/2023. 12 April 2023.

²⁹ ECOS. (2022). Joint call to CEN and CENELEC: Time to give civil society a stronger voice in standardisation. Retrieved from https://ecostandard.org/news_events/joint-call-to-cen-and-cenelec-time-to-give-civil-society-a-stronger-voice-in-standardisation/

³⁰ European Commission. (2022). An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green, and digital EU single market. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions, COM(2022) 31 final.

The findings of this landscape report do point to something under-research, however. On top of the strain put on the standardisation system following the perceived politicisation in the standardisation landscape, the intersection of regulation, harmonised standards and software is increasing the pace of the convergence of open source and standardisation. This, in turn, creates even more demands on inclusivity in the standardisation system.

C4.2 Software, Traditional Standards and Open Source

In chapter 1, the softwarisation of society was pointed to as the primary driver of change in the ICT standardisation landscape: “Software is eating the world”. A parallel development, which many of the interviewees stressed, is that “Open source is eating software faster than software is eating the world.”³¹ As outlined by Hoffman et. al (2024), this is supported by recent research that suggests that open source software, which is publicly available for use and modification, is now prevalent in 96% of codebases and makes up to 99.9% of some commercial software. In fact, the supply-side value of open source software is estimated to be 8.8 trillion dollars.³² Or in professor Frank Nagle’s words: Open source “is a whole swath of the economy itself”³³.

A significant trend highlighted by many interviewees is the perceived lack of understanding within the European policy circles regarding the strategic importance of open source. While the EU Standardisation Strategy acknowledges open source by encouraging European standardisation organisations to integrate open source solutions into their activities to help SMEs achieve quick interoperability,³⁴ a number of interviewees express concern that its importance is not fully recognised at the strategic level in discussions about, for example, digital sovereignty. Additionally, the European standardisation system may be underestimating open source as a tool for developing high-quality standards quickly for the implementation of new software regulations. As such, open source could both be a source of new demand pressures on the European standardisation system, and a tool to meet the growing demands for speed, inclusivity and quality.

Open source and standardisation have interacted in several ways over the years, but with new EU regulations and their respective calls for harmonised standards, in particular from the CRA, the convergence of these two systems of collaborative innovation is accelerating. The questions and challenges, but also the benefits, that arise at the intersection of the open source development model and the standards development model have been the focus of ample debate among practitioners, scholarly investigation and policy analysis for years. Studies such as those by Gamalielsson et al. (2021) and Blind and Böhm (2019), for example, highlight the

³¹ Jacks, J. (2022). Open Source Is Eating Software FASTER than Software Is Eating The World. Retrieved May 5, 2024, from <https://www.coss.community/cossc/open-source-is-eating-software-faster-than-software-is-eating-the-world-3b01>

³² Hoffmann, Manuel and Nagle, Frank and Zhou, Yanuo, The Value of Open Source Software (January 1, 2024). Harvard Business School Strategy Unit Working Paper No. 24-038, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4693148> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4693148>

³³ Nagle, F. (2023). Open Source Software: The \$9 Trillion Resource Companies Take for Granted. Retrieved May 5, 2024, from <https://hbswk.hbs.edu/item/open-source-software-the-nine-trillion-resource-companies-take-for-granted>

³⁴ European Commission. (2022). An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green, and digital EU single market. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions, COM(2022) 31 final.

critical interplay between OSS implementations and the broader standardisation process. Academics and policymakers, while acknowledging the challenges which come with this convergence, often in the form of frictions related to culture, governance, and IPR policies, generally continue to advocate for more collaboration.³⁵

The dialogues around OSS and standardisation with the interviewees reveal a growing recognition of their mutual influence. Michael Eslamian of Huawei Technologies remarks on the dual functionality in the market: “Standards and open source serve different but increasingly complementing functions, with both needed for implementing regulations in digital markets.” This emerging trend is complemented by observations from Mr. Prenter of FSA, who notes that “the relationship between open source and standardisation is growing closer, particularly when software implementations provide exemplary interfaces for standards”.

Mr. Langel emphasises the synergistic relationship: “Open source and standards are complementary. To simplify it somewhat: open source focuses on software and practical implementation, while standards often shape the data structures used by software.” Professor Jakobs of RWTH Aachen adds: “Open source and standards are closely linked yet distinct. Wise entities should engage in both open source developments and ICT standardisation to harness the benefits of both arenas.”

While there is complementarity, and while there is a need to collaborate around the creation of harmonised standards for software, the interviewees generally agree that the challenge is shifting towards how these two cultures—open source communities and standard development organisations—interact, adapt, and evolve to meet the demands of modern regulatory and technological environments.

■ C4.2.1 DIFFERENT DEMANDS FROM SOFTWARE STAKEHOLDERS FOLLOWING REGULATION

The evolution of European regulatory frameworks introduces new challenges and demands on legacy standardisation systems, particularly in the context of representing and integrating open source interests. All software is not open source, but a majority of it is, and it is relevant to the standardisation landscape, as harmonised standards for the software realm are being requested and developed.

Bryant highlights these challenges, stating, “European regulatory ambitions challenge the agility and inclusiveness of legacy standardisation systems, which may not adequately represent open source interests.” This observation points to particularities of the demands for inclusivity and attention from software stakeholders, as opposed to SMEs, civil society and environmental groups. Traditional standardisation might struggle to adapt to the nature of software development and its close use of open source ecosystems.

Further compounding this issue, Ms. Bryant notes a “structural mismatch in standardisation bodies that makes it difficult for open source communities and smaller entities to participate effectively.” This mismatch underscores a significant barrier for open source communities,

³⁵ Gamalielsson, J., & Lundell, B. (2021). *On Engagement With ICT Standards and Their Implementations in Open Source Software Projects: Experiences and Insights From the Multimedia Field*. *International Journal of Standardization Research (IJSR)*, 19(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJSR.287102>; OpenForum Europe. (2017). *Standards and Open Source: Bringing Them Together*. Retrieved from <https://www.openforumeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/StandardsandOpenSourceBringingthemtogether.pdf>; Blind, K., & Böhm, M. (2019). *The Relationship Between Open Source Software and Standard Setting*. In N. Thumm (Ed.), *JRC Science for Policy Report*, EUR 29867 EN. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/163594>

which often operate on principles of transparency, collaboration, rapid iteration, and zero-friction values that are not always reflected in the more rigid and formalised standard-setting processes traditionally dominated by national bodies and larger patent-holding corporations.³⁶

Simon Phipps, in his 2023 commentary for the Open Source Initiative, elaborates on these challenges from a policy perspective. He discusses the European Commission's consideration of open source in policy deliberations, stressing the emergence of a "fourth sector" beyond the traditional commercial, labour, and consumer sectors. This sector is shaped by the internet and open source movement and represents a blend of roles from the traditional sectors.

However, he argues that open source is not well-represented in current consultation mechanisms, leading to policy decisions that may not fully understand or accommodate open source's unique challenges and what it can bring to the table to solve today's challenges following regulation of the software realm. Arguably, this challenge extends to standardisation as well.³⁷

■ C4.2.2 TWO CULTURES MEETING

The ongoing dialogue between OSS communities and SDOs has traditionally focused on overcoming intellectual property and governance challenges. However, this interaction now also grapples with the complexities introduced by new regulatory landscapes. As regulatory attention increasingly pivots towards the software market, the urgency to navigate the intricacies of this relationship intensifies. Ms. Bryant states that "The Cyber Resilience Act marks a significant convergence between open source stakeholders and traditional standards, presenting both challenges and opportunities for integration." For the CRA, there is an implementation deadline, so the collaboration between OSS and standardisation must now rapidly evolve to address the compounded challenges brought forth by the regulatory scrutiny of the software market.

Ms. Bonewald anticipates a risk of dominance of de facto standards if the cultural and working differences between standard bodies and open source groups are not constructively solved: "I think what's going to happen is you are going to watch a lot of de facto standards getting out there simply because of the culture clashes that I see happening between standards bodies and the open source community," suggesting also that speed is of the essence.

Mr. Haack of DIN emphasises the necessity of integration and points to work being done in Germany: "DIN is running a project to integrate open source approaches into standardisation, aiming to make standards more implementable, user-friendly, and open. We also provide a point of contact for open source projects and stakeholders. Ultimately, we want to contribute to bringing the two worlds of standardisation and open source closer together and thus exploiting synergies." His view is echoed by Mr. Karachalios of IEEE, who notes that "Progress in integrating open source with standards shows potential for reducing tension between these communities if a pragmatic approach to intellectual property is maintained."

Mr. Haack develops the reasoning behind DIN's project and his work: "I advocate for a uniform approach through standardisation, emphasising the importance of bringing diverse parties to the table to achieve consensus - a crucial element for laws such as the CRA. In this spirit, I

³⁶ This is investigated in more detail in Blind, K., & Böhm, M. (2019). The Relationship Between Open Source Software and Standard Setting. In N. Thumm (Ed.), JRC Science for Policy Report, EUR 29867 EN. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/163594>

³⁷ Phipps, S. (2023, July 11). Modern EU policies need the voices of the Fourth Sector. Open Source Initiative. <https://opensource.org/blog/modern-eu-policies-need-the-voices-of-the-fourth-sector>

extend an earnest appeal to open source communities to actively engage in standardisation efforts. Participation not only fosters inclusivity but also offers the opportunity for all voices to contribute to shaping the consensus, ensuring that our collective efforts reflect the diverse perspectives and needs of society."

Debra Bryant highlights that there are "Efforts underway to align legislative intentions [of the CRA] with practical actions to include the open source community in the standardisation process, but challenges in defining effective participation remain." An example of changes taking place in the open source ecosystem to adapt to the standardisation system in place is the recently launched collaborative effort led by prominent open source foundations, such as the Apache Software Foundation, Python Software Foundation, and Eclipse Foundation. These organisations have announced a joint initiative to establish common specifications for secure software development in response to the CRA. Aiming to leverage existing best practices within the open source community to align with cybersecurity standards. The project acknowledges the challenges of aligning diverse security practices across open source communities and standards organisations, given the increasing demands of modern cybersecurity regulations.³⁸

C4.3 IPR Policies and Resistance to Change

The intersection of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and standardisation remains a critical focal point within the European ICT standardisation system. On the one hand, it forms part of the current "social contract" that incentivises stakeholder to invest resources into standardisation. At the same time, the ICT standardisation landscape is demanded to rapidly transform due to geopolitical priorities and regulatory extension into software. The interviewees point to how the expectations of zero-friction collaboration in the software realm puts pressure on the existing IPR regimes structuring the standardisation system. While not the main focus of this landscape report, the sensitive question of the friction around fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory (FRAND) licensing norms, the economic value that rests on this regime, and how this interact with software development norms where zero-friction collaboration is expected and royalty-free (RF) licensing is the norm, is pointed to as a key point of resistance to change within the ICT standardisation landscape.³⁹

Echoing the significance of IPR in shaping the standardisation landscape, Ms. Comparin of Thales remarks, "IPR policy has always had huge consequences in standardisation." This sentiment is widely acknowledged across the interviewees. For instance, Mr. Karachalios of IEEE observes that "Standards and intellectual property are central to technological battles for supremacy, with significant geopolitical implications on international standard-setting organisations." It is in itself a factor that is cross-cutting in the standardisation landscape, being relevant in regulation, geopolitics, SDO governance, and European innovation policy. IPR policies is arguably where the world of hardware and software meets.

Mr. Prenter of FSA addresses another facet of this complexity, focusing on the patenting processes and how it affects the work in standards bodies: "The process of companies patenting work after introducing it during standards bodies to seek royalties is now akin to a

³⁸ For more information see: <https://outreach.eclipse.foundation/open-source-cybersecurity-specifications>

³⁹ For an in-depth analysis of these differences see Blind, K., & Böhm, M. (2019). The Relationship Between Open Source Software and Standard Setting. In N. Thumm (Ed.), JRC Science for Policy Report, EUR 29867 EN. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/163594>

business model in and of itself.” This also suggests that there are direct economic interests in maintaining the IPR policy status quo.

Mr. Clark of OASIS Open highlights the strategic role of open source in this context: “Open source work is pivotal for prototyping and proof of concept in standards, which are often pushed towards royalty-free models to ensure broad accessibility.” This exemplifies to some extent how royalty-free licensing frameworks are the norm in the realm of open source, and by extension software in general, and what is a source friction between the software model of collaborative innovation and certain SDOs IPR policies.

Highlighting the benefits of the existing IPR policies, Dirk Weiler states that certain changes to IPR policies that favour standards and open source collaboration could inadvertently disadvantage European ICT champions, like Nokia and Ericsson, in favour of non-European competitors in their markets. He further comments on the perceived shift of Europe becoming a net-licensee of patents and states that the assertion that Europe's influence is waning is contested, with evidence pointing to a diverse and evolving SEP-holder landscape where Europe is still a key player.

Observations from Alexander Prenter are more critical of the status quo. He argues that there is now a business model of standardisation: “with companies increasingly seeking patents after contributing to standards, particularly in telecommunications like 4G and 5G.” He also notes that, “...licensing disputes are becoming more prevalent as the industry shifts to lower-margin sectors like IoT.”

Finally, there are elements of IPR policies not related to the technology being licensed (FRAND and RF), but the standards documents themselves. Zero-friction technological collaboration in the realm of software, and this is particularly relevant for open source development, requires standards to be freely and publicly available, which directly counters the practice of charging for copyrighted standards.⁴⁰

Charging for published standards is a central tenet to the business model for standards organisations, which points to an additional point for friction for change. Mr. Ganesh of CEN-CNELEC adds to this discussion from the point of view of an ESO: “Issues including access to standards and how standards are deployed in the market impact the business of standardisation and are increasingly being addressed by European standardisation bodies and their members.”⁴¹

There is friction that occurs when software and standardisation converge. And the pressure is building to solve this friction. However, working cultures and IPR are still contentious challenges, and the established standardisation system has legacy structures that hinder rapid change. This final section of the final chapter on IPR policies and resistance to change has deservedly been the focus of ample scholarly research and debate. This forms the last part of the gordian knot that European policymakers and standards professionals are looking to untangle: more standards, faster, or higher quality, while the existing institutions' business models are under strain.

⁴⁰ Open Source Initiative. (2006). Open Standards Requirement (OSR) for Software. Retrieved from <https://opensource.org/osr>

⁴¹ Note that the bulk of the interviews took place before the decision of the ECJ in the Malamud case, which is expected to have effects for the copyright of harmonised standards.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The first chapter of this landscape report sets up the broader discussion and contextualises the interviews. The main driver of change in the ICT standardisation landscape is the softwarisation across societal sectors. This is reshaping social interactions and infrastructures and this, in turn, affects ICT standardisation across the board. This chapter also gives background to the two secondary drivers of change that the following chapters go into in depth: new EU regulation and geopolitical rivalries.

The second chapter of this landscape report, the experts interviewed discuss two main trends surrounding digital market regulation and standardisation. One is the concentration in digital markets, noting how major technology firms strategically manoeuvre to influence standardisation, often to protect their market dominance. This, together with concerns around safety and security of digital products and services, drives the second trend, EU regulation extending into software. The subsequent harmonised standards that will bring presumption of conformity in the now regulated software realm grows the number of stakeholders in the ICT standardisation landscape. Taken together, softwarisation of society, regulation and market concentration creates new demands and strain on the European standardisation system.

The third chapter highlights the intensified geopolitical rivalries, particularly between Europe, the USA, and China, which affect the standardisation system. These rivalries not only influence the strategic decisions within standardisation processes but also impact Europe's wish and ability to assert its standards globally. Europe is, among other things, responding to the politicisation of standardisation with demands of reform of ESO governance to increase the influence of governments and national standardisation bodies.

In the fourth chapter, the convergence of software and traditional standards is discussed extensively. Open source is outlined in detail as an example of the new challenges that the regulatory extension into software leads to, touching among other things how it puts demands on changes to IPR policies in ESOs. It also notes the potential this convergence of open source and standardisation holds. New EU regulations rapidly driving forth this convergence have encouraged a reevaluation of traditional approaches, and it is also creating new demands for a more inclusive and collaborative standardisation environment that incorporates diverse stakeholder interests, in particular open source stakeholders that don't necessarily fit the traditional multi-stakeholder mould. This chapter ends with comments how IPR policies of the SDOs is a central point of friction that creates resistance to change in the system.

The profound transformation of the ICT standardisation landscape is predominantly driven by the digitisation and softwarisation of society, a change that reshapes interactions, processes, and infrastructures across all sectors. This sweeping integration of digital technologies serves as a catalyst for broader systemic transformations, which are further spurred by secondary drivers such as EU regulations and geopolitical rivalries. These dynamics in the broader landscape are reshaping the demands on the standardisation system. These demands can be conflicting: demanding agility and inclusivity in developing new standards that can keep pace with rapid technological advancements and complex regulatory environments.

Competing Goals of the EU standardisation strategy

One way to read the statements by the interviewees for this landscape report is that they highlighted several conflicting goals of the European Standardisation Strategy:

2. **Innovation vs. Regulatory Compliance:** rapid innovation might challenge industries to keep pace with regulatory compliance, especially with complex and emerging technologies.
3. **Digital Sovereignty vs. International Cooperation:** Prioritising technological independence could create tension with the need for international collaboration, particularly in areas where global interoperability is crucial.
4. **Global Leadership vs. Market Fairness:** Asserting EU values internationally might create challenges in balancing trade policies, particularly with trading partners that do not share the same standards and priorities.
5. **Speed vs. Quality:** Accelerating the pace of developing and adopting standards may conflict with ensuring comprehensive, high-quality outputs. A quicker process could lead to less thorough stakeholder engagement and oversight.
6. **Inclusivity vs. Efficiency:** Balancing broad stakeholder involvement (including SMEs, civil society) with efficiency in decision-making can be difficult. Too many participants may slow the process, while too few can lead to exclusion and limited perspectives.

These competing goals are well appreciated by the European policymakers, and have been extensively covered by research and policy analysis. What emerged as more novel and nuanced from the interviews, however, was the perceived shift of the demands of the broader ICT standardisation landscape following the rapid convergence between the innovation and collaboration models in the realm of software and a European standardisation system built for a world of hardware and physical products. Arguably, this creates even more complexity in the system, in particular for finding the right balances between speed, quality, inclusivity and efficiency.

In conclusion, the ESOs and the European standardisation system are under strain: more standards are requested at record speed, integrating representation from a growing group of stakeholders while achieving broader political and social goals and maintaining technical quality and relevance. This is at a time when the sustainability of the ESOs' business models is in question, and the political demand for companies to invest in standardisation does not seem to be met by European companies in the same way as by, for example, Chinese companies.

EU regulations and geopolitical tensions further complicate the landscape. Regulations aimed at securing privacy, security, and interoperability directly influence the adaptation of standards within the regulatory framework. Meanwhile, geopolitical tensions reflect concerns about national security and economic competitiveness, affecting technology policy and standards.

Traditional industries are grappling with software-centric standards, while new stakeholders such as software entities are entering traditional standards domains. This influx challenges traditional standardisation paradigms, such as governance and IPR policies, and underscores the need for a more dynamic and responsive standardisation process that can swiftly integrate diverse technological innovations and regulatory requirements.

The intersection of IPR and software standardisation creates tension in the landscape, and creates resistance to change. Interviewees have diverging views when it comes to both the problem formulation and what reforms would bring apt solutions. Established economic

interests, regulation, and legacy institutional structures form on the one hand a system that has been successful at creating quality standards, global interoperability and establishing trust in products in the past. On the other, this system seems resistant to change facing the myriad of new demands being put on it. This highlights the complexities European policymakers and standards professionals must navigate to adapt to evolving geopolitical and technological priorities.

This landscape report, which forms phase 2 of a broader, multi-phased study of Europe's place in a changing ICT standardisation landscape under the StandICT.eu project, draws the preliminary conclusion that the European standardisation processes must evolve to become more agile and inclusive at the same time. This push for agility is not just about speeding up processes but also enhancing the capacity to incorporate a broader spectrum of technologies and stakeholders, ensuring standards remain relevant in the face of rapid technological changes and increasingly complex global challenges.

Next follows a series of recommendations by the author. These should be considered preliminary, and will be further developed in Phases 3 and 4 of the broader study. These recommendations will in the next phase be circulated to interested stakeholders for evaluation, and in the coming months this analysis will be complemented by a number of case studies.

PRELIMINARY POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

These preliminary policy recommendations are based on the conclusions from the landscape report. They represent the start point for discussions to arrive at a final set of recommendations. These recommendations will be expanded and refined throughout a review process within the consortium and stakeholders through the StandICT.eu stakeholder consultation process.

The views expressed and the policy recommendations in this landscape report are solely those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the policy positions of the European Commission, the experts interviewed or the people giving editorial support. They are not necessarily endorsed by the other members of the StandICT.eu consortium and community.

The central findings of this landscape report emphasise the increasingly complex and often competing demands placed on ESOs. While the challenges are multifaceted and fluid, the trade-offs for standardisation in Europe—and perhaps globally—revolve around a constant re-balancing between speed and quality and inclusive representation. While it was not planned at the outset of this landscape report, the majority of discussions circled around the ESOs, and thus the recommendations tend to focus on them, as well as Regulation 1025/2012.

The recommendations presented below aim to enhance the openness and inclusiveness of the European standardisation system, while efficiency, agility and speed should be sought through additional and bold policy efforts. This includes considering 1) drastically increasing the support for the existing ESOs, including financial support, 2) innovating through the inclusion of other, parallel frameworks for collaborative innovation, such as the open source model.

An additional finding central to the recommendations is the fundamental differences between hardware and software, and how this leads to differences in approaches needed to standardisation. The old systems are not necessarily fit for purpose.

Finally, a number of research topics are put forward, which we encourage the European Commission to fund research projects for.

Overarching Recommendations:

- **Evaluate the impact of prioritising the quality of standards and inclusive representation in the standardisation process without compromising them for the sake of speed and efficiency. This remains valid as the political pressure to find fast solutions will most likely increase.**
- **Increase the demand for expertise of policy makers in the European standardisation field to not only include expertise in standardisation, but also additional sectoral expertise, such as software.**

a. Recommendations to Increase Inclusiveness and

Transparency of the ESOs:

- **Incentivise SMEs Participation:** Investigate ways to increase funding opportunities to support the participation of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in standardisation efforts. This could help address resource constraints and enable a broader range of stakeholders to contribute to standard-setting processes.
- **Promote Greater Transparency in SDOs:** Advocate for enhanced transparency within Standards Development Organisations (SDOs). One possible way to achieve this is by publishing regular updates on ongoing standardisation activities, ensuring all stakeholders can stay informed and participate effectively.
- **Modernise Transparency and Access:** Assess how revising Article 4 of Regulation 1025/2012 could provide better access to standards and improve the ability to contribute feedback, accommodating more diverse stakeholders.

Research Recommendation 1: Assess the state of how organisations can partner with ESOs through liaison agreements and partnerships, examining incentives for ESOs to work with external expert groups, particularly in fields where they lack a historical track record such as software. Investigate how Annex III organisations can be better supported to facilitate the inclusiveness of diverse voices into standardisation.

Recommendations to Increase Agility of the System:

- **Address Intellectual Property Conflicts in order to Avoid Resistance to Needed Reform:** Develop clear guidelines on resolving intellectual property conflicts, particularly in harmonised standards related to open source software and royalty-free models. Our conclusions posit that while FRAND can remain the norm for hardware standards, royalty-free should be the norm for harmonised standards that are software-related. All software-related harmonised standards should be available free of charge in order to ensure that the open source stakeholders can use them for presumption of conformity.
- **Increase Financial Support for ESOs:** Consider the funding model of ESOs, for example by increasing financial support for existing ESOs to meet the rising demands placed on them amid changing and complex requirements and the strain on their business models.
- **Update the New Legislative Framework (NLF):** Address efficiency improvements and include software priorities in the upcoming NLF review, in particular for the processes of conformity assessments, and making sure that the named economic operators' roles and responsibilities reflect the realities of software as well as hardware, without overhauling the established framework.
- **Expand Eligible Standards Organisations:** Consider expanding the range of eligible standard development organisations under Regulation 1025/2012 to include entities beyond the ESOs, in particular look to stakeholders in the software realm, who do not fall within the mould of companies or stakeholder representatives.

Research Recommendation 2: Explore the feasibility of creating a fourth ESO specifically focused on software. In the early 1990s, there was a proposal to establish sectoral standards bodies to improve stakeholder representation and expedite the process. This led to the creation of ETSI as a third ESO. However, the Commission's plan to establish additional sectoral ESOs faced strong opposition from stakeholders and was eventually abandoned. This should be revisited.

Open Source and Standardisation Recommendations:

This landscape report identifies the critical role of open source in the ICT standardisation landscape. However, there's a gap between the recognition of open source in EU policy discourse and its significant role in the economy and society. As open source continues to be a driver of technological innovation and digital transformation, accounting for trillions in global economic value, it warrants a more significant policy focus.

Compared to the strategic attention given to open source within standardisation, the EU maintains a comprehensive framework to facilitate standardisation through various entities like the High-Level Forum, Chief Standardisation Officer, and the Multi-Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation. These represent a strategic approach to standardisation that ensures sovereignty, competitiveness, and innovation. Meanwhile, open source lacks the same level of strategic support, receiving less policy attention than standardisation despite its pervasive presence and transformative potential.

To fully harness the potential of open source and ensure a more balanced policy focus, the following recommendations aim to bolster open source collaboration, governance, and integration with the EU's broader standardisation landscape:

- 1. Include Open Source in Broader Policies:** Integrate open source considerations into European research and innovation policies to align stakeholder incentives with the European Green Deal and industrial strategies. Standardisation policies should explicitly encourage collaboration between ESOs and open source projects to foster consistent standards across all sectors.
- 2. Create a Forum for Open Source coordination:** This forum would convene stakeholders from government, industry, academia, and civil society to provide strategic guidance on open source policies. The forum would align open source activities with EU standardisation goals and identify opportunities for collaboration between standardisation bodies and open source initiatives.

Research Recommendation 3: Analyse how the open source model can complement the standards development process within ESOs or provide formal support, particularly for software-related standards. This should also investigate how to incentivise open source institutions to support and partner with European institutions and ESOs to achieve regulatory and standardisation goals.

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